

Profit-optimal Data-Driven Operation of a Hybrid Power Plant Participating in Energy Markets under Forecast Uncertainties

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Introductory Summary

An energy management system (EMS) is formulated for a hybrid power plant (HPP) participating in bidding stages in the German energy market. The stochastic optimization within the EMS aims to maximize the HPP economic profit by balancing the revenue obtained by market bidding and the cost of battery cyclic damage, while explicitly considering the uncertainties associated with generation and price forecasts. The formulation utilizes data-driven probabilistic models trained using site-specific historical measurements, as well as a novel online cycle counting approach. When compared with standard formulations, the proposed approach shows an accurate estimation and balancing of revenue and costs and a significant reduction in the power deviation penalty, which leads to significantly higher overall profit.

Keywords: *Economic dispatch, Battery degradation, Online cycle counting, Power tracking, Hybrid power plant control, Probabilistic forecasting*

Introduction

The variability of wind generation creates fluctuations in the electricity market prices. Additionally, wind speed is also typically negatively correlated with the electricity price [1]. Wind farm owners -as price-takers in the electricity market- suffer from these fluctuations, which tend to reduce revenue, and contribute to the overall need for ancillary services. To tackle these challenges, one emerging approach involves hybridizing the wind power plant (WPP) with other systems such as batteries. Operating such a hybrid power plant (HPP) in an optimal manner within the electricity market can help maximize profit, while improving system reliability and stability.

An energy management system (EMS) facilitates the participation of HPPs in energy markets. State-of-the-art HPP-EMSs aim to maximize the overall revenue while utilizing battery energy storage (BES) to compensate for deviations from the optimal power reference, due to forecast errors and generation variability [2]. Such approaches fail to consider the cost of battery degradation, which may have a significant impact on the overall profit. More advanced HPP-EMS approaches do consider battery damage. However, simplified battery models are typically used and the cost of cyclic damage is approximated within the optimization [3].

The objective of this work is to develop a profit-optimizing EMS that 1) is based on a data-driven generation forecast model, 2) takes into consideration the power generation forecast and market price forecast uncertainties, and 3) considers directly and explicitly the cost of battery cyclic damage. An HPP controller (HPP-C) is formulated to ensure the fulfilment of the EMS optimal power reference. The HPP profit is quantified and the benefits due to the integration of measurement data and an improved optimization formulation are assessed and compared to a standard formulation. The deviation between reference and generation is particularly crucial as it necessitates the deployment of grid ancillary services by the system operator, for which the HPP owner can be heavily penalized. In this context, another objective of this work is to assess the HPP tracking performances for different EMS optimization cases.

Methods

A probabilistic wind forecast is obtained using a machine learning-based model that utilizes Gaussian mixture distributions formed by superimposing several normal distributions. The resulting probability distribution is given by

$$p(x) = \sum_i^n w_i \cdot N(x|\mu_i, \sigma_i), \quad (1)$$

where w_i represents the weight, μ_i the mean and σ_i the standard deviation of the i -th Gaussian normal distribution. In order to find a suitable number n of normal distributions for the mixed distribution, a hyperparameter optimization was performed. Different fully connected neural networks (FCNNs) were trained to predict the parameters w_i , μ_i , and σ_i . Due to the long forecast horizon, an ensemble method consisting of FCNNs was utilized, which combines state-of-the-art numerical weather predictions (NWP) with historical measurement data, this way generating a site-specific forecast of wind speed and direction. Each network is trained only on a specific segment of the overall forecast horizon, resulting in higher forecast accuracy on that segment. The final forecast is a superposition of the output of multiple ensemble networks for that segment. A formulation with four networks offered a good compromise between robustness and training time reduction. The wind condition forecast is given as input to an engineering wake model that simulates the wind farm. The parameters of the wind farm model are tuned offline using site-specific measurement data [4], to accurately capture wake interactions within the farm and predict the power generation from individual turbines. Probabilistic market price forecasts are obtained using the same approach as wind condition forecasts, where the respective FCNNs are trained only using historical market price data.

Access to the energy market is implemented in a stage-wise manner, where HPP first participates in a day-ahead (DA) bidding stage, which is then followed by an hour-ahead (HA) bid-revision stage. The EMS optimizer uses the wind power forecaster, market price forecaster, battery model, and battery current state of charge (SOC) to calculate the total power that the HPP should generate over a time interval, as well as the share of WPP generation that maximizes profit. The stochastic optimization considers power generation and price uncertainties through statistical scenarios. These scenarios not only follow the distribution of the probabilistic forecasts, but also account for the interdependence structure of the prediction error. The scenarios are generated using the method described in [5], followed by scenario reduction using the k-medoids clustering method [6]. The optimization objective function can be mathematically written as

$$\max \sum_s^S \sum_t^T \rho_s \cdot \left(\sum_m \lambda_{s,t}^m \cdot b_t^m - C_{s,t}^{cyc} - w_{penalty} \cdot |\delta_{s,t}| \right). \quad (2)$$

For a given scenario s , the HPP revenue for the current market m is estimated as the product of market price λ_t^m and respective power bids b_t^m for each time interval t of the forecast horizon T . The cost of battery damage $C_{s,t}^{cyc}$ is estimated and minimized directly using the parametric online rainflow counting (PORFC) approach [7]. The PORFC algorithm uses a pre-processing step to identify fatigue cycles and splits the respective damages over the contributing samples. Furthermore, the optimization is subject to penalty constraints to ensure that the deviation $\delta_{s,t}$ between the summed (pre-)bidding for both the DA and HA stages and the operational set-point of the HPP is minimized.

The inevitable short-term forecast errors are compensated, post-market-closure, using wind farm curtailment and/or battery reserves. The HPP-C is formulated as a rule-based controller that, depending on wind farm power availability, decides to either curtail the wind farm or generate the available power. The remaining power goes as a reference to the battery, depending on the battery current SOC, to ensure fulfilment of the HPP reference. As WPP power tracking is of key importance to maximize performance, the implementation is based on a tracking margin-boosting wind farm active power controller, which reduces the occurrence of saturation events of individual turbines [8].

Results and Conclusions

The considered conceptual HPP is supposed to participate in the German energy market and consists of a 60MW WPP combined with a 12MW/12MWh BES. Within the HPP-EMS, both DA and HA bidding stages are considered. The optimal HPP power reference and WPP reference are sent to the HPP-C every 15 minutes. The HPP-C is executed every minute and the battery SOC update is sent back to the EMS.

The proposed EMS optimization case (henceforth referred to as *proposed*) is compared with the most straightforward formulation (henceforth referred to as *standard*) without using site-specific historical data, where the EMS utilizes NWP models for deterministic wind power prediction and aims to maximize HPP revenue. Both cases use BES to compensate for deviations. The net economic profit of the HPP owner is calculated as the difference of revenue, cost and penalty. Revenue is calculated as a product of market bids and respective actual prices for both DA and ID markets. Cost is calculated as the replacement cost of the battery cyclic degradation. Penalty is calculated as the product of HPP generation error and balancing energy (*reBAP*) price.

Figure 1 shows the performance of the HPP participation in the German energy market for an initial assessment period of 24 hours in March 2019. Figure 1a shows the time series of HPP power

Figure 1. HPP participation in the German energy market.

bid, battery SOC, and cumulative HPP power deviation over the assessed duration, whereas Fig. 1b shows the economic metrics, for both the formulated cases. Owing to more accurate forecasts in the *proposed* case due to the explicit consideration of uncertainties using historical data, the HPP bids a considerably smaller capacity in the market compared to the *standard* case (compare the blue curve with the orange curve in the top subplot in Fig. 1a). This also leads to not only a reduction in battery cycling (refer to the central subplot in Fig. 1a) but also to a smaller cumulative power deviation (refer to the bottom subplot in Fig. 1a). Additionally, the direct consideration of the cost of battery damage within the EMS optimization in the *proposed* case further ensures that the battery is cycled only when there is a positive economic value to it. Hence, the SOC profile in the *proposed* case is characterized by multiple cycles of relatively small depths, in contrast to the large cycles of the *standard* case. Thus, although the *standard* case results in a higher revenue than the *proposed* case, as shown in Fig. 1b, the former also incurs significantly higher penalties and an increased cost of battery damage. As a consequence, the *proposed* EMS formulation results in an approximately 17% higher profit than the *standard* formulation.

The conference presentation will discuss multiple intermediate formulations, highlighting the relative improvements brought by the individual aspects of the proposed formulation. This includes consideration of forecast uncertainties, battery damage minimization, data-driven tuning of wind farm model, wind farm power tracking control, and others. The analysis will also be performed over a longer assessment period, to demonstrate more accurately the benefits of considering uncertainties within the HPP operation in the energy market.

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